

Education of Msmes in the Order of Improving Product Sales by Using Digital Media in the Middle of the Covid-19 Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The ongoing COVID-19 pandemic throughout the world has had a tremendous impact on people's lives. Not only the health sector, but the economic sector is also paralyzed due to the Covid-19 pandemic, one of the affected countries is Indonesia. This pandemic has greatly affected the economic activities of the community. As a result, many types of businesses experience losses, as happened to MSMEs in the city of Cilegon. During this pandemic, technology has an important role, people prefer to buy everything they need through their smartphones. In the end, it was MSMEs that had utilized technology that were able to survive. The potential of using technology for MSME business development is very influential. Therefore, the role of technology at this time is very large, so the main focus is developing the business of MSME partners to be online-based by utilizing social media, websites and existing market places and developing the potential of each MSME partner who has been assisted.

KEYWORDS

MSMEs;
Covid;
digital media;
social media

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1. Introduction

The ongoing Covid-19 pandemic in almost all of the world has had a tremendous impact on people's survival [1]. Not only the health sector, but the economic sector is also paralyzed due to the Covid-19 pandemic, one of the affected countries is Indonesia [2]. The Covid-19 pandemic that hit Indonesia had a huge impact, especially on the economy [3]. Where this pandemic greatly affects the economic activities of the community [4]. As a result, many types of businesses have losses, as happened to MSMEs in Cilegon City [5]. MSMEs located in the city of Cilegon are one of the areas affected by the Covid-19 pandemic, where many MSMEs have experienced a very significant decline in income since this pandemic entered Indonesia. As a result, not a few MSMEs finally closed their businesses because they were unable to survive in the midst of a pandemic. If on the one hand there are MSMEs that have experienced a decline in income due to the Covid-19 pandemic, on the other hand, there are MSMEs that are not affected by the pandemic, and some have even experienced an increase in income. In this time of pandemic, technology has an important role, people prefer to buy everything they need through their smartphones. Until in the end, it was MSMEs that had utilized technology that was able to survive.

Several studies on technology for MSMEs have been investigated. Research on digital media is used for this community service. Connected audiences in the digital media market: The dynamics of the impact of university online videos researched by López-Buenache by [6]. Making a place outside the city through the lens of digital media: Culturally diverse youth negotiating social change in a rural city is researched by Waite [7]. Preliminary evidence of 50% reduction in contrast media using digital variance angiography in carotid endovascular intervention was studied by riás [8]. Behavior of User Generated Content and digital tourism services: A SEM neural network model for information trust in social networking sites was

investigated by Kitsios [9]. The integrated use of social media, digital, and traditional communication tools in the international SME B2B sales process was researched by Fraccastoro [10]. A New Approach to Social Media Privacy Education Through Role Reversal Simulation is researched by Ghazinour [11]. Digital media in institutional informal learning settings: A systematic literature review researched by Degner [12]. How variations in internet access, digital skills, and media use relate to rural student outcomes: GPA, SAT, and educational aspirations were investigated by Hampton [13]. Young patients with cancer and digital social networks: voices outside the clinic researched by Ben-Aharon [14]. Digital marketing activity by a Dutch place management partnership: A resource-based view researched by Hagen [15].

Site-Specific Education Using Digital Media to Improve Patient Understanding of Radiotherapy Pathways: An Intervention Study investigated by Almerdhemah [16]. Reliable sources of travel and tourism information from social media: perspective of international tourists visiting Ethiopia studied by Berhanu [17]. Analyzing the factors that influence information seeking and sharing in smart city digital platforms: Empirical evidence from Indonesia was researched by Kusumastuti [18]. Digital art - a useful tool for medical professionals to create medical illustrations researched by Appukuttan [19]. No two gangs are alike: The digital divide in the differential adaptation of street gangs to social media was researched by Whittaker [20]. New digital rights: Envisioning additional fundamental rights for the digital age is researched by Custers [21]. How digital marketing evolved over time: Bibliometric analysis of the Scopus database researched by Faruk [22]. Modeling influence and community in social media data using the digital initiative-twitter capture and analysis toolkit (DMI-TCAT) method and Gephi researched by Groshek [23]. Is Covid-19 accelerating digital entrepreneurship opportunities? The Indian perspective was investigated by Modgil [24]. Species identification morphological evidence of wildlife forensics based on digital images investigated by Trail [25].

Explosion of digital storytelling. The creator's perspective and the creative process on the new narrative form were investigated by Sanchez-Lopez [26]. Combating digital addiction: Current approaches and future directions researched by Cemiloglu [27]. Individual responsibility, collective problem: Framing of dietary practices in the Latvian media was investigated by Orste [28]. A method for observing the elastic behavior of anisotropic porous materials using digital image correlation was investigated by Manzari [29]. The interaction of the Dark Triad and social media using motifs for social media distraction was investigated by Tang [30]. Setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and research propositions researched by Dwivedi [31]. The potential of digital tools to improve mathematics and science learning in secondary schools: A context-specific meta-analysis investigated by Hillmayr [32]. How to digitize vocational teachers? Assessing digital competence in vocational education and looking at the underlying factors investigated by Cattaneo [33]. Countering violent extremism using social media and preventing strategies that can be applied to Bangladesh is researched by Amit [34]. Platform drifting: When digitizing the work of hijacking the spirit is researched by Rahrovani [35].

Based on this background, community empowerment contributes to mobilizing MSMEs by using digital media technology programs. The potential of using technology for MSME business development is very influential. Because in addition to MSME business actors do not need to make physical contact with buyers directly, MSME business actors can also still sell and earn income from home. Therefore, the role of technology at this time is very large, so the main focus is developing the business of MSME partners to be online-based by utilizing social media, websites and existing market places and developing the potential of each MSME partner who has been assisted. . Previously, MSME partners only knew that the use of technology was important. Now MSME partners have been able to manage and utilize existing technology to increase their sales, such as using social media, websites and market places. In addition to MSME partners knowing how to use existing technology, partners also know knowledge related to their business such as IT, Branding, Intellectual Property Rights, and legal counseling.

2. Method

The activity plans in order to implement the solutions offered, in detail are:

- Implementation of the Go-Online MSME program, where this program is a learning and training program about social media, market places, and websites that will be accompanied directly 5 – 15 August 2020

- Implementation of the UMKM program in action, where this program is a learning and training program on intellectual property, legal counseling, product design and photos that will be accompanied directly 5 -26 August 2020
- Implementation of the Covid-19 response, where this program is a campaign activity to spread information about Covid-19 which will be held 30 July – 29 August 2020.

3. Results and Discussion

The service members make visits to the homes of SMEs to find partners who will be assisted, these activities are shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Visits to MSME owners

After searching for partners, 2 MSMEs were found, namely Mama Opey's kitchen and mavw.id. Shown in figure 2

Fig. 2. The process of finding MSME partners

The servants held the first meeting with all MSME partners and discussed the programs to be implemented, shown in Figure 3

Fig. 3. First meeting with all partners

The mentoring process begins with the delivery of masks, hand sanitizers, and face shields as part of the #responsecovid19 program which aims as a symbolic form of and support for MSME partners in the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic, shown in Figure 4

Fig. 4. Symbolic handover of masks and hand sanitizer to assisted partners

The next activity was the delivery of material about photography, namely product photos using a smartphone camera, after that it was continued with the delivery of material on photo editing using the VSCO application, after that it was continued with product photo training directly by MSME Partners who were present who had brought various kinds of their products. after that it was continued with the delivery of material about design using the Canva application and pixel labs, shown in Figures 5 and 6

Fig. 5. Photography

Fig. 6. Design

The next mentoring activity was by delivering material on social media and followed by training, namely using a business Instagram account and making Inktree. Then proceed with the introduction and creation of websites and marketplaces with training on Shopee marketplace governance, shown in Figure 7

Fig. 7. Website

Servants accompany MSME partners in carrying out IT and Branding lessons as well as learning about IPR through zoom, shown in Figures 8 and 9

Fig. 8. Implementation of IT Learning and Branding

Fig. 9. Implementation of learning about IPR

Not only mentoring in learning and introduction to IT and Branding, but also servants accompanying partners in carrying out learning about counseling through zoom, shown in Figure 10.

Fig. 10. Implementation of legal counseling activities

After carrying out various lessons, training and counseling to MSME partners, then further assistance was carried out to directly carry out product photos that would be marketed directly to MSMEs, Mama Opey and mavw.id kitchens, shown in Figures 11 and 12

Fig. 11. Making photos of mama opey's kitchen products

Fig. 12. Making mavw.id product photos.

4. Conclusion

The KKN-PPM Program Located in Cilegon, namely the empowerment of MSMEs based on information and communication technology to help MSMEs affected by COVID-19. Where this pandemic has greatly affected the economic activities of the community. As a result, many types of businesses have losses, as happened to MSMEs in Cilegon City. The potential of using technology for MSME business development is very influential. Because in addition to MSME business actors do not need to make physical contact with buyers directly, MSME business actors can also still sell and earn income from home. Therefore, the role of technology at this time is very large, so the main focus is developing the business of MSME partners to be online-based by utilizing social media, websites and existing market places and developing the potential of each MSME partner who has been assisted. . In addition to MSME partners knowing how to use existing technology, partners also know knowledge related to their business such as IT, Branding, Intellectual Property Rights, and legal counseling. The MSME partners who have been assisted and assisted by the servants are MSMEs from the Kitchen Mama Opey business house and Mavw.id.

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